

DIRECT COMPARISON OF CF/EPOXY LAMINATES AND ITS NEAT RESIN IN MODE I INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS AND FATIGUE DELAMINATION AT RT AND 77K

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SUMMARY: The mode I interlaminar fracture toughness and delamination fatigue of carbon fiber (CF)/epoxy laminates were compared with those of the neat resin. Tests were carried out both at room temperature (RT) in laboratory air and at 77K in liquid nitrogen (LN₂). CF/epoxy laminates were made from prepregs of HTA/113 (Toho Tenax). Unidirectional laminates of (0)₂₂ and the nominal thickness of 3 mm were molded in an autoclave. Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness and delamination fatigue tests for laminates were carried out using double cantilever beam specimens. Those for the neat resin were evaluated using compact (C(T)) specimens cut from epoxy 113 slabs of the thickness of 10mm. The mode I fracture toughness of the neat resin, 113, was 83 J/m² at RT in air and 182 J/m² at 77K in LN₂. Thus, the toughness increased by 2.2 times by changing the test environment from RT in air to 77K in LN₂. Contrary to the resin properties, the toughness of laminates was almost insensitive to the test environment. On the other hand, the fatigue crack growth resistance of epoxy 113 and HTA/113 were almost the same in the low rate region for both environments. Moreover, the increase of the fatigue properties by changing the test environment from RT in air to 77K in LN₂ was 2.6 to 2.9 times for both epoxy 113 and HTA/113. These ratios are similar to that for the static fracture toughness of epoxy 113. Fractographic observation indicates that the contribution of resin under fatigue loading is much larger than that under static loading. Then, the increase of the resin toughness by changing the test environment from RT in air to 77K in LN₂ only contributes to the fatigue properties.

KEYWORDS: interlaminar fracture toughness, fatigue delamination, CFRP laminates, neat resin, liquid nitrogen

INTRODUCTION

Although two decades have passed since the importance of the interlaminar fracture was recognized [1,2], the individual contribution of mesoscopic structures such as fiber, matrix resin, interface and their geometrical distribution still remains to be understood [3,4]. Though the neat resin has been regarded to play the most important role in the interlaminar fracture properties of composite laminates, there are only a few studies on the direct comparison of the fracture properties between the neat resin and its composite laminates [5-8]. Specially, only the report of Lang et al. is available for this comparison under fatigue loading [9]. This is due to the difficulties in getting the neat resin plaque from prepreg suppliers. Thus, it is rather hard to separate the resin effect on the complicated interlaminar fracture process in composite laminates

under fatigue loading.

Carbon fiber (CF)/epoxy laminated structures are the candidates for the cryogenic tanks in space vehicles [10]. Then, the evaluation of interlaminar properties under static and fatigue loadings at cryogenic temperature is important from the structural integrity. Since resin properties are sensitive to the test temperature, the tests at different temperatures give clear comparison how the change of resin property is translated into interlaminar properties of composite laminates.

In the present study, the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness and delamination fatigue crack growth properties of carbon fiber (CF)/epoxy laminates were compared with those of the neat resin. Tests were carried out both at room temperature (RT) in laboratory air and at 77K in liquid nitrogen (LN₂). The contribution of resin in delamination is discussed on the basis of fracture mechanics and microscopic fracture mechanism considerations.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

CF/epoxy laminates used in this study were made from prepregs of HTA/113 (Toho Tenax). HTA is a high strength type PAN based carbon fiber, and 113 is a bisphenol A type epoxy resin with the curing temperature of 393 K. Unidirectional laminates of (0)₂₂ and the nominal thickness of 3 mm were molded in an autoclave. The volume fraction of fiber was 60% using the combustion method. Slabss of epoxy 113 (100x100x10 mm) were molded for the measurement of the neat resin properties. The curing temperature was 393 K. The glass transition temperatures (T_g) of the neat epoxy 113 and HTA/113 laminates were measured using a differential scanning calorimeter (DSC, Rigaku, Thermo Plus DSC 8230) and based on JIS 7121-1987. T_g for 113 was 397 K and that for HTA/113 was 399 K. This agreement indicates that the microstructure of the matrix resin in CFRP laminates is similar to that in the neat resin slabs for the present study.

Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness and delamination fatigue tests for laminates were carried out using double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens [11-13]. Fig. 1 shows the DCB specimen. Special loading apparatus with universal joints was used for all tests [11,13]. Starter slits were introduced into the specimen by inserting 12.5 μm thick polyimide film during molding. The surface and edge of the film were coated with a mold release agent before molding. Mode I precracks of lengths of 2 mm were introduced into the specimens by clamping the specimens across the entire width approximately at the end of the starter slits and then manually wedging open the specimens [12,13].

Fig. 1. Double cantilever beam specimen (Dimensions are in mm).

Fig. 2. Compact specimen.

Fig. 3. Loading apparatus and setup for HTA/113 laminates at 77 K in LN₂.

Compact (C(T)) specimens [14] of 25x24x10 mm (Fig. 2) were cut from Epoxy 113 slabs. The specimens were heat-treated at 413 K (about 15 K above the glass transition temperature) for 1 hr followed by slow cooling at the rate of 5 K/min to reduce the residual stress during curing. Precracks of 1 to 2 mm were introduced into the C(T) specimens by tapping razor blades [15].

The energy release rate, G , for C(T) specimens were calculated from the stress intensity factor, K [14], using $G=(1-\nu^2)K^2/E$ where ν is the Poisson's ratio and E is the elastic modulus of the neat resin. The neat resin elastic modulus, E , was 3.9 GPa at RT and 7.6 GPa at 77 K. The energy release rate, G , for DCB tests under mode I loading was calculated using the modified compliance calibration method [12,13]. The initial values of the fracture toughness, G_{Ic} , were evaluated using the nonlinear point which were determined by the point of deviation from linearity in the initial load-displacement curves.

All the tests were carried out in a computer-controlled servohydraulic testing system (Shimadzu 4880, 9.8 kN) with original software [4,11,16] A load cell of 490 N capacity was attached for tests. Tests at 77 K were carried out in LN₂ using a cage type load frame (Fig. 3) [15,16]. The specimens were first placed about 5 mm above the liquid nitrogen surface followed by dipping

deep in liquid nitrogen for about 30 minutes. Tests were started after the liquid nitrogen had stopped boiling. Since the thickness of the neat resin C(T) specimen is large, the neat resin tests were started after dipping the specimen for about 80 minutes. The cross head speed was controlled to be 0.1 mm/min in DCB tests [12,13] and 0.5 mm/min in C(T) tests [16].

For fatigue tests, the stress ratio, R , of the minimum load to the maximum load was kept constant to be 0.1 and 0.5. For HTA/113 laminates, the fatigue tests at RT in air were carried out by keeping the maximum energy release rate constant to avoid the effect of fiber bridging (G_{\max} -constant test) [17]. Only the normal load shedding tests by keeping the maximum crack opening displacement constant were carried out at 77 K in LN_2 . Here, the resulting normalized gradient of the energy release rate, $(1/G)dG/da$, was -0.10 to 0.12 mm^{-1} . For the neat 113 epoxy, the fatigue crack growth tests were carried out based on ASTM E647-95a with the back face strain measurement [18]. $(1/G)dG/da$ was controlled to be -0.1 mm^{-1} at RT in air. Tests at 77 K in LN_2 were carried out by controlling the maximum strain at back face constant. Here, the resulting normalized gradient of the energy release rate, $(1/G)dG/da$, was -0.08 to 0.12 mm^{-1} . The frequency of stress cycling was 10 Hz. The crack length, a , was computed from the measurement of the compliance for tests with both DCB and C(T) specimens [11,18].

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Fracture toughness of neat resin

The fracture toughness value of the neat epoxy 113 at RT in air was 83 J/m^2 and that at 77 K in LN_2 was 180 J/m^2 . Thus the toughness increased by 2.2 times by changing the test environment from RT in air to 77 K in LN_2 . Similar increase was observed for the neat bisphenol A type epoxy in our separate study [15]. Brown has reported that the stress-strain behavior of all polymers, amorphous and crystalline, is affected by N_2 at low temperatures [19]. Kneifel has reported that the fracture toughness of epoxy at 77K in LN_2 is higher than that at RT in air and

Fig. 4. Effect of temperature on relation between mode I fracture toughness and increment of crack length.

at 5 K in LHe, and that the reason for this is the reduced notch effect by plastic deformation [20]. Then, the increase of the fracture toughness of the neat epoxy 113 in this study was probably caused by the similar effect.

2. Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of laminates

The crack growth at RT in air was stable for HTA/113 laminates. On the other hand, stick-slip behavior was observed for tests at 77 K in LN₂. Then, the maximum points of each serration pattern in the load-crack opening displacement relations were used for the calculation of the propagation values of the energy release rate, G_{IR} , because these points correspond to the stable crack growth. The relation between the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness and the increment of the crack length (R-curve) is presented in Fig. 4. In this figure, the open and solid marks indicate the results at RT in air and at 77 K in LN₂. The G_{Ic} of the neat resin in both environments are also depicted by arrows in this figure.

The data points at $\Delta a=0$ (average at RT in air = 111 J/m², 77 K in LN₂= 115 J/m²) correspond to the initial values of the fracture toughness, G_{Ic} , at the nonlinear point. The toughness values sharply increased from the initial values, G_{Ic} , and then leveled off where Δa is larger than 1 to 2 mm. The average of the plateau region of G_{IR} was calculated as 123 J/m² at RT in air and 136 J/m² at 77 K in LN₂ when Δa is larger than 2 mm. Thus, although the neat epoxy 113 fracture toughness increased by 2.2 times by changing from the test environment from RT in air to 77 K in LN₂, the interlaminar fracture toughness of the HTA/113 laminates remained almost constant. It is interesting to note that the toughness of HTA/113 at RT in air is slightly higher than that of the neat epoxy 113 while the toughness of HTA/113 at 77 K in LN₂ is much lower than that of the neat epoxy 113. The reason for this difference will be discussed later in the microscopic observation.

Fig. 5. Comparison of fatigue crack growth behavior between neat resin and CF/epoxy laminates.

Fig. 6. Comparison of fracture toughness and fatigue threshold for neat resin and CF/epoxy laminates at RT in air and 77 K in LN₂.

3. Fatigue crack growth tests of neat resin and laminates

Fig. 5 shows the relationship between the crack propagation rate, da/dN , and the maximum energy release rate, G_{Imax} at RT in air, which corresponds to the maximum load during fatigue loading. In this figure, the results of the neat epoxy 113 are indicated by open marks. da/dN is expressed as power functions of G_{Imax} in the region where da/dN is larger than 10^{-9} m/cycle. For the HTA/113 laminates, only the data points corresponding to the zero increment of the crack growth [17] are depicted by solid marks. The figures associated with the lines indicate the exponents of the power functions. These exponents are rather high (9 to 13) and also similar between the neat epoxy 113 and HTA/113 laminates. The downward deviations from the power functions are clear both for the neat epoxy 113 and HTA/113 laminates. The results of the neat epoxy 113 agree well with those of HTA/113 laminates specially near the threshold region.

Fig. 6 compares the static fracture toughness values and the fatigue threshold values at RT in air and at 77 K in LN₂ for both the neat epoxy 113 and HTA/113 laminates. The downward deviations from the power functions were not observed for the fatigue crack growth behavior in LN₂. However, the exponents (8 to 35) are large enough to indicate the existence of the growth threshold. Then, the G_{Imax} values at $da/dN=10^{-9}$ m/cycle are used as the threshold values in Fig. 6. Contrary to the results of the fracture toughness tests, the agreement between the threshold values of the neat epoxy 113 and that of the HTA/113 laminates are quite good, indicating the resin properties are directly translated to the laminate properties. The ratios of the threshold values at 77 K in LN₂ to that at RT in air are 3.1 (R=0.1) and 2.8 (R=0.5) for the neat epoxy 113, and are 2.9 (R=0.1) and 2.6 (R=0.5) for the HTA/113 laminates. These ratios are slightly higher than that for the static fracture toughness of the neat epoxy 113 of 2.2.

The equivalent stress intensity range, ΔK_{eq} , is expressed as below as a controlling parameters for fatigue crack growth of composite laminates under various R values[21,11]:

Table 4. Feature of fracture surface in HTA/113 laminates.

$$\Delta K_{eq} = \Delta K \cdot \gamma \cdot K_{max} \quad (1)$$

where the stress-ratio effect parameter, γ ($0 \leq \gamma \leq 1$), indicates the relative contribution of the maximum load to the cyclic load in determining the crack growth rate. The γ values are obtained from the experimental relationship between ΔK at a given da/dN and $(1-R)$ [21]. The γ values for the neat resin are 0.67 (RT in air) and 0.95 (77 K in LN₂), and those for the HTA/113 laminates are 0.72 (RT in air) and 0.83 (77 K in LN₂). These higher γ values indicate that the fracture mechanism of the neat resin and the laminates is rather controlled by the maximum load.

Table 4 summarizes the feature of the fracture surface for the HTA/113 laminates observed in scanning electron microscopy. Interfacial fracture was dominant for the static fracture toughness tests and contribution of resin was larger for the fatigue delamination tests. Although thermal compressive residual stresses at fiber/matrix interface become larger at 77K, the interfacial fracture may initiate at the point where the residual stress is minimum because the absolute value for the CF/epoxy is not so large [16,22]. Then, for the case of the static fracture toughness tests, the interfacial fracture concealed the contribution of the increase of the neat resin fracture toughness on the CF/epoxy laminates toughness by changing the test environment from RT in air to 77 K in LN₂. On the other hand, the contribution of the resin fracture is rather high for the fatigue delamination of the laminates, and the increase of the resin crack growth resistance is directly translated to the crack growth resistance of the CF/epoxy laminates. This can also be understood by lower fiber bridging density observed at 77K in LN₂.

CONCLUSIONS

The mode I fracture properties of the neat epoxy 113 and the HTA/113 laminates were compared for the mode I fracture toughness and the fatigue crack growth behavior at RT in air and at 77 K in LN₂. The results are summarized as follows:

(1) The interlaminar fracture toughness of the HTA/113 laminates is slightly higher than that of the neat epoxy 113 at RT in air. On the other hand, the toughness of the HTA/113 laminates is much lower than that of the neat epoxy 113 at 77 K in LN₂. The fracture toughness of the neat epoxy 113 increased by 2.2 times by changing the test environment from RT in air to 77 K in LN₂. The interlaminar fracture toughness of the HTA/113 laminates is rather insensitive to the test environment.

(2) The fatigue growth thresholds of the HTA/113 laminates are almost identical to that of the neat epoxy 113 both at RT in air and at 77 K in LN₂. The threshold values at 77 K in LN₂ are about three times higher than those at RT in air.

(3) The difference of the contribution of the resin properties under static and fatigue loading is attributed to the difference in the microscopic fracture mechanism.

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